

First record of the genus *Cardiomya* (Mollusca, Bivalvia, Cuspidariidae) off the Chilean margin and description of a new species

Primer registro del género *Cardiomya* (Mollusca, Bivalvia, Cuspidariidae) frente al margen chileno y descripción de una nueva especie

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ABSTRACT

During a sampling campaign with the R/V SONNE on a transect off Concepción, Chile, in 2023, a specimen of the genus *Cardiomya* was discovered at 912 m water depth. This is the first observation of this genus off the coast of Chile. The specimen is described here as a new species of the genus *Cardiomya*.

RESUMEN

Durante una campaña de muestreo con el R/V SONNE en un transecto frente a Concepción, Chile, en 2023, se descubrió un espécimen del género *Cardiomya* a 912 m de profundidad. Se trata de la primera observación de este género frente a las costas de Chile. El espécimen se describe aquí como una nueva especie del género *Cardiomya*.

KEY WORDS: Chile, *Cardiomya*, Cuspidariidae, Mollusca, SE Pacific Ocean.

PALABRAS CLAVE: Chile, *Cardiomya*, Cuspidariidae, Mollusca, Océano Pacífico Sudeste.

INTRODUCTION

The water masses of the SE Pacific off both Chile and Peru are significantly influenced by the Humboldt Current. This area is one of the most productive marine regions in the world (CUBA ET AL. 2022). Constant currents, winds and induced upwelling with increasing primary productivity lead to considerable oxygen deficiency and development of oxygen minimum zones (OMZs) in

the seabed of the shelf area (BUSECKE ET AL. 2019; KRUG & ZETTLER 2025). Below 400 metres, however, the influence of oxygen-rich water begins to increase the diversity of species on the sea floor. Only recently, a methane seep area with a distinct and adapted fauna was discovered in the area about 70 kilometres off Concepción, and several new species of molluscs have been described (e.g. SELLANES

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ET AL. 2004, 2008). The present study is based on material from exactly the same location at a water depth of between 910 and 930 metres, which was obtained during a research cruise with the R/V SONNE in 2023.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

To investigate the species communities of macrozoobenthos in the centre and at the edge of the oxygen minimum zone off Chile (approx. 36°S), several stations along a depth transect of 56 to 1850 m were sampled at the beginning of 2023 during the research cruise SO296 on the R/V SONNE. With the exception of the deepest station, at each station 3 samples (hauls) were taken with the van Veen grab (1000 cm²). The collected material was sieved with a mesh size of 1 mm on board. A CTD-rosette was used to measure environmental parameters such as temperature, salinity, water

depth and oxygen content. With the help of the CTD, water samples were taken from near-bottom water and used to calibrate the oxygen samples.

All samples were fixed in 4 % borax-buffered formalin or stored directly in 70 % ethanol. The molluscs from these samples were hand-sorted under a low-magnification binocular (Zeiss Discovery.V8) and colour photographs were taken at IOW using a microscope camera (Axiocam 105 color). High-resolution imaging was done using the Scanning Electron Microscope at IOW (FESEM Zeiss Merlin VP compact with Gemini I electron column; acceleration voltage 5-15 KV; 5axis stage with 3-70° tilt function; detectors: SE, VPSE, InLens SE, BSD; Magnification: 12-2.000 000) under vacuum. The SEM sample was coated with gold, by using a Cressington sputter coater for high resolution imaging.

The holotype of the newly described species is deposited in the Senckenberg Museum, Frankfurt am Main (SMF).

SYSTEMATICS

Class BIVALVIA Linnaeus, 1758
Family CUSPIDARIIDAE Dall, 1886
Genus *Cardiomya* A. Adams, 1864

Cardiomya concepcionensis n. sp. (Figs. 1-15)

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Type locality: off the central Chilean margin, 70 km northwest of Concepción, 36.3577°S, 73.7347°W; 912 m; 22 Jan. 2023; Stn. SO296/2-6.

Type material. *Holotype:* CHILE • 1 live-collected specimen (Figs. 1-15); 70 km northwest of Concepción; 36.3577°S, 73.7347°W; 912 m; 22 Jan. 2023; Stn. SO296/2-6, van Veen grab; SMF.

Etymology: Named after the type locality, 70 kilometres NW off the Bay of Concepción.

Diagnosis: Shell length ~9.9 mm, large straight and elongated rostrum, sinuate anterior margin, antero-dorsal margin straight, protruding anteriorly beyond the anterior margin forming a well-marked shoulder, external sculpture composed of about 32 radial ribs over shell disk and 3 clear radial lines on the rostrum.

Description: Semi-transparent shell, white-yellowish, moderately small for

the genus (9.9 mm long and 5.5 mm high), slightly inequivalve, umbos moderately pronounced and in the anterior third, fragile, somewhat inflated, about 32 radial, rounded ribs, spaced more or less equidistant from anterior ventral margin to the rostrum, rostrum with 3 distinct radial lines, transition from the radial ribs of the shell disk to the radial lines of the rostrum fluent without a gap, ventral margin through the ribs

Figures 1-7. *Cardiomya conceptionensis* n. sp., off Concepción, Chilean margin, depth 912 m, holotype, 9 mm. 1: lateral outer view of the right side; 2: lateral outer view of the left side; 3: dorsal view; 4-7: internal view of both valves.

Figuras 1-7. Cardiomya conceptionensis n. sp., frente a Concepción, margen chileno, profundidad 912 m, holotipo, 9 mm. 1: vista lateral externa del lado derecho; 2: vista lateral externa del lado izquierdo; 3: vista dorsal; 4-7: vista interna de ambas valvas.

serrated, most prominent posteroventrally.

Prodissoconch: The boundaries of the prodissoconch cannot be determined

due to corrosion, but should be about 300 μ m in length (Figs 10-15).

Dissoconch: Globose with elongated rostrum; blunt protruding umbo in the

front third of the shell; antero-dorsal margin straight, protruding anteriorly beyond the anterior margin forming a well-marked shoulder; anterior margin slightly sinuate in its upper part; convex ventral margin (Figs 1-2). The surface shell sculpture consisting of 32 strong, regular radial ribs across the entire shell disk and 3 distinct radial lines on the rostrum. Lunule and escutcheon absent. Periostacrum thin, adherent and translucent white to light yellowish (Figs 1-3). Internally smooth and glossy with serrated margin (Figs 1-5, 8, 9). Posterior adductor muscle scars clearly visible, anterior muscle scar undefined (Figs 4-5). Pallial line entire. Hinge plate very narrow. Right valve with only one strong, moderately short, posterior lateral tooth (Figs 4, 6, 8, 10, 14); left valve edentulous (Figs 5, 7, 11, 13, 15). Amphidetic ligament with fibrous part and a calcified lithodesma, deeply located on a subtriangular resilifer placed directly below the umbones (Figs 10-15).

Anatomy: Although the animal was collected alive, it was not possible to examine the anatomy. To prepare undamaged valves, the soft body was dissolved with lye. Mechanical dissection and thus preservation of the soft body seemed too risky and would probably have destroyed the shells.

Ecology: As only one individual was found, little can be said about the ecology of this species. We found it at 912 m water depth on muddy sediment. The salinity was 34.4 psu, the oxygen content of the bottom water 115 $\mu\text{mol/l}$ and the temperature 4.4°C.

Distribution: Only known from the type locality.

Differential diagnosis: We present a comparison with the known species of *Cardiomya* from eastern Pacific (off Alaska to Chile) and south-western Atlantic (off Brazil to Argentina).

According to MOLLUSCABASE EDS. (2025), 54 recent species constitute the genus *Cardiomya*. Of these, only *Cardiomya cleryana* (A. d'Orbigny, 1846) is given for Southern Chile (Patagonia) (CARCELLES 1950), but this is incorrect. The distribution in the Strait of Magel-

lan is not confirmed and refers only to CARCELLES (1950) (see MACHADO *ET AL.* 2017). CARCELLES (1950) refer to SMITH (1915), who found and described this species as *C. simillima*, now a synonym of *C. cleryana*, from Rio de Janeiro and Falkland/Malvinas Islands what definitely does not belong to Chile. The work of SOOT-RYEN (1959) already lists *C. cleryana* with a question mark for the Magellan Province and does not list it for the Chilean fauna. The origin of the FORCELLI (2000) record is not specified and uncertain. The more recent overview monographs do not list the species for this region (e.g. LINSE 1999, 2002; ALDEA *ET AL.* 2020). *C. cleryana* is most probably restricted to the Atlantic waters of Brazil, Uruguay and Argentina (HUBER 2010; MACHADO *ET AL.* 2017; PACHECO *ET AL.* 2024).

The comprehensive overview about the bivalves from northern Peru to southern Chile by VALENTICH-SCOTT *ET AL.* (2020) gives no indication of the genus *Cardiomya* for Peru and Chile. The nearest Pacific occurrences of the genus are in Ecuador (COAN & VALENTICH-SCOTT 2012). These include the species: *C. costata* (G. B. Sowerby I, 1834), *C. didyma* (Hinds, 1843), *C. lanieri* (A. M. Strong & Hertlein, 1937), *C. pectinata* (P. P. Carpenter, 1864) and *C. planetica* (Dall, 1908). All these species are clearly distinguished by a different rib structure and shell shape. Only the number of 35 ribs in *C. planetica* is comparable. However, the latter lacks the lines on the rostrum and the lateral tooth in the right shell is less pronounced (COAN *ET AL.* 2000; COAN & VALENTICH-SCOTT 2012). The well-marked anterodorsal shoulder is also missing. Two other species complete the list of *Cardiomya* that occur along the Pacific North American shelf (COAN *ET AL.* 2000; HUBER 2010). These are *Cardiomya balboae* Dall, 1916 and *Cardiomya behringensis* (Leche, 1883). Both can be easily distinguished from the newly described species by their shape, ribbing and rostrum alone.

Only twelve species of *Cardiomya* are known to occur in the Western Atlantic Ocean (MIKKELSEN & BIELER 2007;

Figures 8-15. *Cardiomya concepcionensis* n. sp., off Concepción, Chilean margin, depth 912 m holotype, 9 mm. 8: lateral internal view of the right valve; 9: lateral internal view of the left valve; 10-13: detailed view of the hinge in both valves; 14, 15: detailed dorsal view on the umbo of both valves.

Figuras 8-15. Cardiomya concepcionensis n. sp., frente a Concepción, margen chileno, profundidad 912 m, holotipo, 9 mm. 8: vista lateral interna de la valva derecha; 9: vista lateral interna de la valva izquierda; 10-13: vista detallada de la charnela en ambas valvas; 14, 15: vista dorsal detallada del umbo de ambas valvas.

Table I. Morphological comparison of *Cardiomya conceptionensis* n. sp. with similar species and from species distributed in Brazilian, Argentinian and sub-Antarctic waters.

Tabla I. Comparación morfológica de *Cardiomya conceptionensis* n. sp. con especies similares y otras especies de aguas de Brasil, Argentina y subantárticas.

Species	Maximum shell length, mm	Number of ribs	Presence of ribs or radial lines on rostrum (number)	Shape and relative size of rostrum	Presence of anterior "shoulder"	Distribution
<i>C. conceptionensis</i> n. sp.	10	32	yes (3)	elongated	yes	Pacific
<i>C. planetica</i>	30	28-35	no	moderately long	no	Pacific
<i>C. cleryana</i>	10.5	22-25	no	short and curved upwards	no	Atlantic
<i>C. fragilissima</i>	23	50	no	short and curved upwards	no	Atlantic, Antarctic
<i>C. knudseni</i>	8.1	26-30	yes (10)	moderately long	yes	Atlantic
<i>C. minerva</i>	4.3	6	no	very short	yes	Atlantic
<i>C. ornatissima</i>	9-13	6-7	no	short	no	Atlantic
<i>C. perrostrata</i>	25	20-25	yes (7-10)	elongated	no	Atlantic
<i>C. striata</i>	19	30-40	yes (5)	short and curved upwards	no	Atlantic
<i>C. striolata</i>	9.3	18-35	yes (1-3)	short and curved upwards	yes	Atlantic

HUBER 2010; MACHADO ET AL. 2017; LIMA ET AL. 2020). Of these, eight species are found in Brazilian and Argentinian waters or even further south in sub-Antarctic waters (PASSOS & MAGELHÃES 2011; MACHADO ET AL. 2017, OLIVEIRA ET AL. 2017; LIMA ET AL. 2020, 2024; PACHECO ET AL. 2024). These are: *C. cleryana* (A. d'Orbigny, 1846), *C. fragilissima* (E. A. Smith, 1885), *C. knudseni* (J. A. Allen & R. E. Morgan, 1981), *C. minerva*

T. C. Lima, C. D. Oliveira & Absalão, 2020, *C. ornatissima* (d'Orbigny, 1853), *C. perrostrata* (Dall, 1881), *C. striata* (Jeffreys, 1876) and *C. striolata* (Locard, 1897). Three other species, which have not yet been fully described, are known from Brazil but differs significantly by ribbing and size (LIMA ET AL. 2020, fig. 6). All the species mentioned above can be easily distinguished from *C. conceptionensis* n. sp. (Table I).

DISCUSSION

Usually, a single specimen consisting only of the shell might not have warranted a description by name (see ALLEN 2011). However, this particular shell is in perfect condition and has such a distinct ornamentation (32 ribs and 3 radial lines on the rostrum), unlike that of any other described species of *Cardiomya*, that an exception has been made. It is also the first time that the genus has been found in waters off Chile. Looking at the distribution of *Cardiomya* on the shelf of Brazil and Argentina (PASSOS & MAGELHÃES 2011; MACHADO ET AL. 2017, OLIVEIRA ET AL. 2017; LIMA ET AL. 2020,

2024; PACHECO ET AL. 2024), it is remarkable that no *Cardiomya* has been detected on large parts of the Peruvian and Chilean shelf (HUBER 2010; VALENTICH-SCOTT ET AL. 2020). On the other side of the Pacific, species of the genus are known at the same latitude, such as *Cardiomya bruuni* Dell, 1956 or *C. rectimarginata* Dell, 1962 off New Zealand (HUBER 2010). Deep-sea molluscs have only been studied sparingly in Chile. It is most likely a question of effort and chance that further findings will become known in the bathyal off Chile and Peru.

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